

Transformation of *p*-Iodo-N, N-Dimethylaniline to Crystal Violet Cation and other Products

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We have reported recently¹, that the reaction of a mixture of iodic acid, iodine, and N, N-dimethylaniline (DMA) gave in addition to *p*-iododimethylaniline at least three other secondary products, viz., N-*p*-dimethylaminobenzyl-N-methylaniline, methylviolet, and an iodo-dye of the crystal violet type.

By extending the time of the above reaction, the yield of *p*-iododimethylaniline was considerably decreased and three more secondary products were isolated in quantities sufficient for their complete characterization. These were identified as N, N, N', N'-tetramethylbenzidine² and the corresponding tetramethyldiphenoquinoneiminium salt,³ and Michler's hydrol⁴. The 'iodo-dye' was identified as hexamethylpararosaniline triiodide (CVI₃).

Seemingly *p*-iododimethylaniline has a role in the genesis of the aforementioned six secondary products of oxidation of DMA. The results reported in this communication establish this view.

p-Iododimethylaniline in methylene chloride gave a colourless solution which turned blue at room temperature within two hours. The blue solution showed absorption at λ_{610-15} μ . This change in colour was greatly accelerated at higher temperatures. The band at λ_{610-15} μ is, presumably, due to a CV-DMA complex of the $Py^+ Py$ type⁴. This was also discerned from a direct comparison of this spectrum with the one of crystal violet (iodide) in DMA, diluted with methylene chloride. The nature of the two curves were found to be strikingly similar.

In presence of traces of acids, the blue solution turned violet; $\lambda(CH_2Cl_2)$ 583-85 μ (due, primarily, to CV cation). Basification of the violet solution, extraction of the liberated bases, and their identification by the usual methods, established the presence of five of the six secondary products (only absence being N-*p*-dimethyl-aminobenzyl-N-methylaniline) mentioned above. Similar spontaneous transformation was also observed with solid *p*-iododimethylaniline at room temperature. *p*-Bromodimethylaniline remained practically unchanged under these conditions.

1. Ghosal, *This Journal*, 1965, 42, 799.
2. Sterba *et al.*, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1965, 30, 2477.
3. König and Seifert, *Chem. Ber.*, 1934, 67B, 2112.
4. Reid and Mulliken, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 3869.

On the basis of the above results, it is considered, that the first phase of this transformation is the dissociation of *p*-iododimethylaniline into the component radicals, — *N,N*-dimethylaminophenyl and iodine. Hydrogen abstraction from one of the two alkyl groups of the former moiety, and suitable coupling of the generated radicals would then result in *N, N, N', N'*-tetramethyl benzidine, *N-p*-dimethylamino benzyl-*N*-methylaniline, and DMA.

Oxidations of *N, N, N', N'*-tetramethylbenzidine to the tetramethyl-diphenoquinone iminium ion⁵ and *N-p*-dimethylaminobenzyl-*N*-methylaniline to CV cation⁵ seem to be well substantiated reactions.

The evidence for the radical production in this reaction was gained from the polymerization of *N*-vinylcarbazole (NVC) with *p*-iodo-dimethylaniline at ca. 70°. This phenomenon is attributable to the presence of iodine radical in the reaction mixture since halogens⁶ are confirmed initiators in the free-radical induced polymerization⁷ of NVC.

Procedure.—All solid products reported here had m. p.s. close to those reported in the literature and had satisfactory elemental analyses. The micro-analyses were performed by Dr. A. Bernhardt, Mulheim (Ruhr), Germany. The visible absorption spectra were taken on Spectronic 20, Bausch and Lomb Colorimeter.

Materials.—E. Merck pure quality crystal violet and DMA, reagent grade methylene chloride, and May and Baker re-sublimed iodine were used.

Separation of the Transformation Products.—The purple-black product obtained from solid *p*-iododimethylaniline (1.0 g.), kept at room temperature for 4 weeks was dissolved in benzene chloroform (1:1) and chromatographed on Brockmann alumina (20 × 1.4 cm). Petroleum (60-80°) 200 ml; petroleum-benzene (90:10), benzene (100), and benzene-chloroform (99:1, 98:2, 90:10, 80:20), 100 ml. each; benzene-chloroform (50:50), 300 ml., and chloroform, 200 ml. were used as the eluents. 40 ml. Fractions were collected.

5. Eastman *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1962 **84**, 1339.

6. Biswas and Ghosal, *Chem. & Ind.*, in press.

7. Scott *et al.*, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1963, 1073.

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TABLE I

Fractions	Product (Wt. in g.)	M. P.	λ_{max} (CH ₂ Cl ₂), m μ
1-5	<i>p</i> -Iododimethylaniline (0.02)	78°	—
20-23	Mixture of tetramethylbenzidine and the dipbenoquinone iminium iodide (0.11)	152-66°	575-68
24-25	CVI ₂ (0.23)	220-23°	355, 585
27-29	Mixture of CVI ₂ and Michler's hydrol blue (0.36)	90-100°	580-89

The individual components were further identified by paper chromatography (Whatman No. 1, CHCl₃-MeOH) using marker compounds, and ceric sulphate as the spraying reagent².

Polymerization of NFC.—In a pyrex glass test tube NYC (0.2 g) and *p*-iododimethylaniline (0.11 g.) were taken. The mixture was rubbed with a glass rod while warming on a steam-bath at 70° for 20 min. The deep-yellow pasty mass was taken in benzene and precipitated with acetone. The straw-coloured polymer was dried *in vacuo*, m.p. >360°.

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